

ANTI FUZZY SOFT GAMMA REGULAR SEMIGROUPS

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Abstract:

In this paper, we have introduced the notion of anti fuzzy soft Γ -semigroups, anti fuzzy soft Γ -ideal, bi-ideal, interior ideal Γ -regular, soft Γ -regular anti fuzzy soft Γ -regular and obtain some interesting properties results and discuss in this paper

Index Terms: Soft set, fuzzy set, Anti fuzzy soft set, soft Γ -semigroups, soft Γ -ideals (bi-ideal, interior ideal), Γ -regular semigroups, and anti fuzzy soft Γ -regular semigroups.

1. Introduction:

The fundamental concept of fuzzy set was introduced by Zadeh [16] in 1965. Sen and Saha [12] defined the Gamma semigroup in 1986. Soft set theory proposed by Molotsov [6] in 1999. Maji et al [5] worked on soft set theory and fuzzy soft set theory. Ali et al [1] introduced new operations on soft sets. Chinram and Jirojkul [3] defined the bi-ideals in Gamma semigroups in 2007. P. Dheena et al [4] studied the characterization of regular Gamma semigroups through fuzzy ideals in 2007. Chinnadurai [2] worked on regular semigroups. Characterized by the properties of anti fuzzy ideals in semigroups proposed by Shabir et al [13] anti fuzzy Gamma bi-ideal introduced in Gamma semigroups studied Nagaiah [9]. Samit Kumar Majumder studied [14] Gamma semigroups in terms of anti fuzzy ideals. Muhammad Gulistan et al [8] presented generalized anti fuzzy interior ideals in LA- semigroups. Sardar et al [11] Characterized Gamma semigroups in terms of anti fuzzy ideals. Sujit Kumar Sardar [14] worked Fuzzy Ideals in Gamma Semigroups. Muhammad Ifran Ali et al [7] studied soft ideals over semigroups. Thawat changphas et al [15] studied soft Gamma semigroups. In this paper, we obtained some results on properties of anti fuzzy soft Gamma semigroups and regular semigroups.

2. Preliminaries:

Definition 2.1 [12]. Let $S = \{a, b, c, \dots\}$ and $\Gamma = \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \dots\}$ be two non-empty sets. Then S is called a Gamma semigroup if it satisfies the conditions

- (i) $a\alpha b \in S$
- (ii) $(a\beta b)\gamma c = a\beta(b\gamma c)$ for all $a, b, c \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.2 [15]. A Γ -semigroup S is called a regular if for each element $a \in S$, there exists $x \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$ such that $a = a\alpha x\beta a$.

Definition 2.3 [4]. Let S be a Γ -semigroup. A non empty subset A of S is called an ideal, an ideal A of S is said to be idempotent $A\Gamma A = A$.

Definition 2.4 [6]. Let U be the universal set, E be the set of parameters, $P(U)$ denote the power set of U and A be a non-empty subset of E. A pair (F, A) is called a soft set over U, where F is mapping given by $F : A \rightarrow P(U)$.

Definition 2.5 [5]. Let (F, A) and (G, B) be two soft sets over a common universe U then (F, A) AND (G, B) denoted by $(F, A) \wedge (G, B)$ is defined as $(F, A) \wedge (G, B) = (H, A \times B)$ where $H(\alpha, \beta) = F(\alpha) \cap G(\beta), \forall (\alpha, \beta) \in A \times B$

Definition 2.6 [5]. Let (F, A) and (G, B) be two soft sets over a common universe U then (F, A) OR (G, B) denoted by $(F, A) \vee (G, B)$ is defined as $(F, A) \vee (G, B) = (H, A \times B)$ where $H(\alpha, \beta) = F(\alpha) \cup G(\beta) \forall (\alpha, \beta) \in A \times B$.

Definition 2.7 [1]. The extended union of two fuzzy soft sets (F, A) and (G, B) over a common universe U is fuzzy soft set denoted by $(F, A) \cup_{\epsilon} (G, B)$ defined as $(F, A) \cup_{\epsilon} (G, B) = (H, C)$ where

$$C = A \cup B, \quad \forall c \in C.$$

$$H(c) = \begin{cases} F(c) & \text{if } c \in A - B \\ G(c) & \text{if } c \in B - A \\ F(c) \cup G(c) & \text{if } c \in A \cap B. \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.8 [1]. The extended intersection of two fuzzy soft sets (F, A) and (G, B) over a common universe U is fuzzy soft set denoted by $(F, A) \cap_{\epsilon} (G, B)$ defined as $(F, A) \cap_{\epsilon} (G, B) = (H, C)$ where $C = A \cup B, \quad \forall c \in C.$

$$H(c) = \begin{cases} F(c) & \text{if } c \in A - B \\ G(c) & \text{if } c \in B - A \\ F(c) \cap G(c) & \text{if } c \in A \cap B. \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.9 [2]. A soft set (F, A) is called a soft semigroup over S if, $(F, A) \overset{\sim}{\circ} (F, A) \subseteq (F, A)$. Clearly a soft set (F, A) over a semigroup S is a soft semigroup if and only if $\phi \neq F(a)$ is a subsemigroup of $S, \forall a \in A.$

Definition 2.10 [7]. A soft semigroup (F, A) over a semigroup S is called a soft regular semigroup if for each $\alpha \in A, F(\alpha)$ is regular.

Definition 2.11 [2]. The restricted product (H, C) of two fuzzy soft sets (F, A) and (G, B) over a semigroup S is defined as $(H, C) = (F, A) \overset{\sim}{\circ} (G, B)$ where $C = A \cap B$ by $H(c) = F(c) \overset{\sim}{\circ} G(c), \forall c \in C.$

Definition 2.12 [16]. Let X be non-empty set. A fuzzy subset μ of X is a function from X into the closed unit interval $[0, 1]$. The set of all fuzzy subsets of X is called a fuzzy power set of X and is denoted by $FP(X)$.

Definition 2.13 [8]. Let X be non empty set and A be subset of X . Then the anti characterization function χ_A^c is defined by soft Γ – semigroup of S .

$$\chi_A^c = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \in A \\ 1 & \text{if } x \notin A \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.14 [11]. A fuzzy set δ of a Γ – semigroup S is called an anti fuzzy Γ – subsemigroup of S if $\delta(x\alpha y) \leq \max\{\delta(x), \delta(y)\}$ for all $x, y \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.15 [11]. A fuzzy set δ of a Γ – semigroup S is called an anti fuzzy Γ – left (right) ideal of S if $\delta(x\alpha y) \leq \delta(y)$ ($\delta(x\alpha y) \leq \delta(x)$) for all $x, y \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.16 [13]. A fuzzy set δ of a Γ – semigroup S is called an anti fuzzy Γ – bi-ideal of S if $\delta(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \max\{\delta(x), \delta(z)\}$ for all $x, y, z \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.17 [13]. A fuzzy set δ of a Γ – semigroup S is called an anti fuzzy Γ – interior ideal of S if $\delta(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \delta(y)$ for all $x, y, z \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.18 [10]. Let δ be a fuzzy subset of a Γ – semigroup S and let $t \in [0, 1]$ then the set $\delta_t = \{x \in S : \delta(x) \leq t\}$ is called the anti level subset of δ .

3. Anti Fuzzy Soft Γ – Semigroups:

In this section S denotes anti fuzzy soft Γ – semigroup and AFS denotes anti fuzzy soft.

Definition 3.1. Let (F_1, A) be AFS set over a Γ – semigroup S , then $(F_1, A) \overset{\sim}{\circ} (F_1, A) \supseteq (F_1, A)$ is called AFS Γ – semigroup.

Example 3.2. $S = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\}$ and $\Gamma = \{\alpha, \beta\}$ where α, β is defined on S with the following Cayley table:

α	a_1	a_2	a_3
a_1	a_1	a_1	a_1
a_2	a_1	a_1	a_2
a_3	a_1	a_1	a_3

β	a_1	a_2	a_3
a_1	a_1	a_1	a_1
a_2	a_1	a_1	a_1
a_3	a_1	a_1	a_1

Table-1

Consider $A = \{a_1, a_2, a_3\}$ and $F(a_1) = \{a_1\}$, $F(a_2) = \{a_1, a_2\}$, $F(a_3) = \{a_1, a_3\}$.

Hence (F_1, A) is soft Γ – semigroup.

Definition 3.3. Let (F_1, A) be AFS set over a Γ – semigroup S, then (F_1, A) is called AFS Γ – subsemigroup of S if, $\delta_e(p\alpha q) \leq \max\{\delta_e(p), \delta_e(q)\}$ for all $p, q \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

Definition 3.4 Let (F_1, A) be AFS set over a Γ – subsemigroup S then (F_1, A) is called AFS Γ – left (right) ideal of S if $\delta_e(p\alpha q) \leq \delta_e(q)$ ($\delta_e(p\alpha q) \leq \delta_e(p)$) for all $p, q \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

Definition 3.5. Let (F_1, A) be AFS set over a Γ – semigroup S, then (F_1, A) is called AFS Γ – ideal of S if, $\delta_e(p\alpha q) \leq \min\{\delta_e(p), \delta_e(q)\}$ for all $p, q \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

Definition 3.6. Let (F_1, A) be AFS set over a Γ – semigroup S, then (F_1, A) is called AFS Γ – bi-ideal of S if, $\delta_e(p\alpha r \beta q) \leq \max\{\delta_e(p), \delta_e(q)\}$ for all $p, q, r \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Definition 3.7. Let (F_1, A) be AFS set over a Γ – semigroup S, then (F_1, A) is called AFS Γ – interior ideal of S if, $\delta_e(p\alpha r \beta q) \leq \delta_e(r)$ for all $p, q, r \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Theorem 3.8. Let (F_1, A) be AFS subset of S. If (F_1, A) be AFS subsemigroup of S if and only if $(F_1, A) \approx (F_1, A) \supseteq (F_1, A)$.

Proof. Let $u \in S$. Assume that (F_1, A) is AFS Γ – subsemigroup of S
 $(F_1, A) \approx (F_1, A) = (H_1, A)$, where $H_1(e) = F_1(e) \approx F_1(e)$ for all $e \in A$.
 Consider

$$\begin{aligned} (F_1, A) \approx (F_1, A)(u) &= \inf_{u=a\Gamma b} \max\{F_1(e)(a), F_1(b)\} \\ &\geq \inf_{u=a\Gamma b} F_1(e)(a\Gamma b) \\ &\geq \inf_{u=a\Gamma b} F_1(e)(u) \\ &= F_1(e)(u) \end{aligned}$$

$$(F_1, A) \approx (F_1, A) \supseteq (F_1, A).$$

Conversely assume that $(F_1, A) \approx (F_1, A) \supseteq (F_1, A) \quad \forall u, v \in S$

Consider

$$\begin{aligned} (F_1(e)(u\Gamma v)) &\leq \{F_1(e) \approx F_1(e)\}(u\Gamma v) \\ &= \inf_{u\Gamma v=a\Gamma b} \max\{F_1(e)(a), F_1(b)\} \\ &\leq \max\{F_1(e)(u), F_1(e)(v)\} \end{aligned}$$

Hence (F_1, A) be AFS subset of a Γ – subsemigroup of S

Theorem 3.9. Let (F_1, A) be AFS subset of a Γ – semigroup S. Then the following conditions hold.

(i) (F_1, A) be AFS Γ – left ideal of S if and only if $(S, E) \approx (F_1, A) \supseteq (F_1, A)$.

(ii) (F_1, A) be AFS Γ – right ideal of S if and only if $(F_1, A) \approx (S, E) \supseteq (F_1, A)$.

Proof. We prove that (i) holds. Assume that (F_1, A) be AFS Γ – left ideal of S $(S, E) \approx (F_1, A) = (H_1, A)$ where $H_1(e) = S(e) \approx F_1(e) \quad \forall e \in A$.

Consider

$$\begin{aligned} ((S, E) \circledast (F_1, A))(u) &= \inf_{u=a\Gamma b} \max\{S(e)(a), F_1(e)(b)\} \\ &\geq \inf_{u=a\Gamma b} \max\{0, F_1(e)(a\Gamma b)\} \\ &= \max\{0, F_1(e)(u)\} \\ &= F_1(e)(u) \end{aligned}$$

So $(S, E) \circledast (F_1, A) \supseteq (F_1, A)$.

Conversely assume that $(S, E) \circledast (F_1, A) \supseteq (F_1, A)$.

Let $u = a\Gamma b$ then we have

$$\begin{aligned} F_1(e)(a\Gamma b) &= F_1(e)(u) \\ &\leq \{S(e) \circledast F_1(e)\}(u) \\ &= \inf_{u=p\Gamma q} \max\{S(e)(p), F_1(e)(q)\} \\ &\leq \max\{S(e)(a), F_1(e)(b)\} \\ &= \max\{0, F_1(e)(b)\} \\ &= F_1(e)(b) \end{aligned}$$

Hence (F_1, A) is AFS Γ – left ideal of S

(ii) Similar proof.

Theorem 3.10. Let (F_1, A) be AFS Γ – subsemigroup of S . Then (F_1, A) is AFS Γ – bi-ideal of S if and only if $(F_1, A) \circledast (S, E) \circledast (F_1, A) \supseteq (F_1, A)$.

Proof. Let (F_1, A) is AFS Γ – bi-ideal of S, then

$$(F_1, A) \circledast (S, E) \circledast (F_1, A) = (H_1, A) \text{ where } H_1(e) = F_1(e) \circledast S(e) \circledast F_1(e) \text{ for all } e \in A.$$

Let $u \in S$ such that $u = a\Gamma b$ and $a = p\Gamma q$.

$$\text{We have } F_1(e)(p\Gamma q\Gamma b) \leq \max\{F_1(e)(p), F_1(e)(b)\}$$

Consider

$$\begin{aligned} F_1((e) \circledast S(e) \circledast F_1(e))(u) &= \inf_{u=a\Gamma b} \{\max\{(F_1(e) \circledast S(e))(a), F_1(e)(b)\}\} \\ &\geq \inf_{u=a\Gamma b} \left\{ \max \left\{ \inf_{a=p\Gamma q} \{\max\{F_1(e)(p), S(e)(q)\}\} F_1(e)(b) \right\} \right\} \\ &= \inf_{u=a\Gamma b} \left\{ \max \left\{ \inf_{a=p\Gamma q} \{\max\{F_1(e)(q), 0\}\} F_1(e)(b) \right\} \right\} \\ &= \inf_{u=p\Gamma q\Gamma b} \{\max\{F_1(e)(p), F_1(e)(b)\}\} \\ &\geq \inf_{u=p\Gamma q\Gamma b} F_1(e)(p\Gamma q\Gamma b) \\ &= F_1(e)(u) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $F_1(e) \circledast S(e) \circledast F_1(e) \supseteq F_1(e)$ for all $e \in A$.

Conversely assume that $F_1(e) \circledast S(e) \circledast F_1(e) \supseteq F_1(e)$

Let $a, b, c \in S$ and $u = a\Gamma b\Gamma c$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_1(e)(a\Gamma b\Gamma c) &= F_1(e)(u) \\
 &\leq \{F_1(e) \circ S(e) \circ F_1(e)\}(u) \\
 &= \inf_{u=x\Gamma y} \{ \max\{F_1(e) \circ S(e)\}(x), F_1(e)(y) \} \\
 &\leq \max\{ \{F_1(e) \circ S(e)\}(a\Gamma b), F_1(e)(c) \} \\
 &= \max\left\{ \inf_{a\Gamma b=p\Gamma q} \{ \max\{F_1(e)(p), S(e)(q)\} \}, F_1(e)(c) \right\} \\
 &\leq \max\{ \max\{F_1(e)(a), S(e)(b)\}, F_1(e)(c) \} \\
 &= \max\{ \max\{F_1(e)(a), 0\}, F_1(e)(c) \} \\
 &= \max\{F_1(e)(a), F_1(e)(c)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence (F_1, A) is AFS Γ – bi-ideal of S.

Theorem 3.11. Let (F_1, A) AFS be subset of a Γ – semigroup of S . If (F_1, A) is AFS Γ – bi-ideal of S then $(F_1, A) \circ (F_1, A) \supseteq (F_1, A)$ and $(F_1, A) \circ (S, E) \circ (F_1, A) \supseteq (F_1, A)$.

Proof. By theorem (3.8) and (3.10) we get the required results.

Theorem 3.12. Let (F_1, A) be AFS Γ – subset of a Γ – Semigroup S . Then (F_1, A) is AFS soft Γ – interior ideal of S if and only if $(S, E) \circ (F_1, A) \circ (S, E) \supseteq (F_1, A)$.

Proof

Assume that (F_1, A) is AFS Γ – interior ideal of S, now

$(S, E) \circ (F_1, A) \circ (S, E) = (H_1, A)$ where $H_1(e) = S(e) \circ F_1(e) \circ S(e)$ for all $e \in A$.

Let $u \in S$ such that $u = a\Gamma b$ and $a = p\Gamma q$.

We have $F_1(e)(p\Gamma q\Gamma b) \leq F_1(e)(q)$

Consider

$$\begin{aligned}
 (S(e) \circ F_1(e) \circ S(e))(u) &= \inf_{u=a\Gamma b} \{ \max\{ \{S(e) \circ F_1(e)\}(a), S(e)(b) \} \} \\
 &= \inf_{u=a\Gamma b} \left\{ \max\left\{ \inf_{a=p\Gamma q} \{ \max\{S(e)(p), F_1(e)(q)\} \}, S(e)(b) \right\} \right\} \\
 &\geq \inf_{u=a\Gamma b} \left\{ \max\left\{ \inf_{a=p\Gamma q} \{ \max\{0, F_1(e)(q)\} \}, 0 \right\} \right\} \\
 &\geq F_1(e)(u)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $S(e) \circ F_1(e) \circ S(e) \supseteq F_1(e)$

Conversely assume that $S(e) \circ F_1(e) \circ S(e) \supseteq F_1(e)$

Let $u, w, v \in S$

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_1(e)(u\Gamma w\Gamma v) &\leq \{S(e) \tilde{\circ} F_1(e) \tilde{\circ} S(e)\}(u\Gamma w\Gamma v) \\
 &= \inf_{u\Gamma w\Gamma v=p\Gamma q} \{\max\{S(e) \tilde{\circ} F_1(e)\}(p), S(e)(q)\} \\
 &\leq \max\{(S(e) \tilde{\circ} F_1(e))(u\Gamma w), S(e)(v)\} \\
 &= \max\{(S(e) \tilde{\circ} F_1(e))(u\Gamma w), 0\} \\
 &= \inf_{u\Gamma w=p\Gamma q} \{\max\{S(e)(p), F_1(e)(q)\}\} \\
 &\leq \max\{S(e)(u), F_1(e)(w)\} \\
 &= \max\{0, F_1(e)(w)\} \\
 &= F_1(e)(w).
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence (F_1, A) is AFS Γ – interior ideal of S.

Theorem 3.13 Let (F_1, A) be AFS subset of S. Then (F_1, A) is AFS subsemigroup of S if and only if $\tilde{U}((F_1, A): [t_1, t_2])$ is AFS subsemigroup of S.

Proof. Assume that (F_1, A) is AFS subset of S. Let $[t_1, t_2] \in [0, 1]$ such that $p, q \in \tilde{U}((F_1, A): [t_1, t_2])$ then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta_{F_1(e)}(p\alpha q) &\leq \max\{\delta_{F_1(e)}(p), \delta_{F_1(e)}(q)\} \\
 &\leq \max\{[t_1, t_2], [t_1, t_2]\} \\
 &= [t_1, t_2]
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus $pq \in \tilde{U}((F_1, A): [t_1, t_2])$. Hence $\tilde{U}((F_1, A): [t_1, t_2])$ is AFS Γ – subsemigroup over S. Conversely, assume that $\tilde{U}((F_1, A): [t_1, t_2])$ is AFS Γ – subsemigroup of S, for all $[t_1, t_2] \in [0, 1]$ and

$p, q \in S, \alpha \in \Gamma$. Suppose $\delta_{F_1(e)}(p\alpha q) > \max\{\delta_{F_1(e)}(p), \delta_{F_1(e)}(q)\}$ then there exists an element $x \in [0, 1]$ such that $\delta_{F_1(e)}(p\alpha q) > x > \max\{\delta_{F_1(e)}(p), \delta_{F_1(e)}(q)\}$, which implies that $\delta_{F_1(e)}(p) > x$ and $\delta_{F_1(e)}(q) > x$ then we have $p, q \in \tilde{U}((F_1, A): x)$. Hence $\delta_{F_1(e)}(pq) < x$ which is a contradiction, then we have $p, q \in \tilde{U}((F_1, A): x)$.

Theorem 3.14. Let (F_1, A) and (G_1, B) be two AFS Γ – ideal (bi-ideal, interior ideal) of S, then $(F_1, A) \wedge (G_1, B)$ is AFS Γ – ideal (bi-ideal, interior ideal) of S.

Proof. Let (F_1, A) and (G_1, B) be two AFS Γ – ideal over S. Now we defined $(F_1, A) \wedge (G_1, B) = (H_1, C)$ where $C = A \times B$ and $H_1(a, b) = F_1(a) \cap G_1(b)$ for all $(a, b) \in C$.

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{H_1(a,b)}(l\alpha m) &= (\delta_{F_1(a)} \cap \delta_{G_1(b)})(l\alpha m) \\ &= \max\{\delta_{F_1(a)}(l\alpha m), \delta_{G_1(b)}(l\alpha m)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\min\{\delta_{F_1(a)}(l), \delta_{F_1(a)}(m)\}, \min\{\delta_{G_1(b)}(l), \delta_{G_1(b)}(m)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\max\{\delta_{F_1(a)}(l), \delta_{G_1(b)}(l)\}, \max\{\delta_{F_1(a)}(m), \delta_{G_1(b)}(m)\}\} \\ &= \min\{(\delta_{F_1(a)} \cap \delta_{G_1(b)})(l), (\delta_{F_1(a)} \cap \delta_{G_1(b)})(m)\} \\ &= \min\{\delta_{H_1(a,b)}(l), \delta_{H_1(a,b)}(m)\} \end{aligned}$$

Hence $(F_1, A) \wedge (G_1, B)$ is AFS Γ – ideal of S.

Theorem 3.15. Let (F_1, A) and (G_1, B) be two AFS Γ – ideal (bi-ideal, interior ideal) of S, then $(F_1, A) \vee (G_1, B)$ is AFS Γ – ideal (bi-ideal, interior ideal) of S.

Proof. The proof is straightforward.

Example 3.16. Every AFS Γ – ideal of S is an AFS Γ – bi-ideal of S, but converse is not true.

From the table.1, Let $E = \{v_1, v_2, v_3\}$, $A = \{v_1, v_3\}$, then (F_1, A) is AFS set defined as

$$\delta_{F_1(v_1)} = \{(a_1, 0.2), (a_2, 0.8), (a_3, 0.5)\},$$

$$\delta_{F_1(v_3)} = \{(a_1, 0.4), (a_2, 0.9), (a_3, 0.7)\}$$

Hence (F_1, A) is AFS Γ – bi-ideal, but not Γ – ideal of S.

Theorem 3.17. Let (F_1, A) and (G_1, B) be two AFS Γ – ideal of S, then $(F_1, A) \cap_{\epsilon} (G_1, B)$ and $(F_1, A) \cup_{\epsilon} (G_1, B)$ is AFS Γ – ideal of S.

Proof. Let (F_1, A) and (G_1, B) be two AFS Γ – ideal of S then $(F_1, A) \cap (G_1, B) = (H, C)$ where $C = A \times B$,

$$H_1(c) = \begin{cases} F_1(c) & \text{if } c \in A - B \\ G_1(c) & \text{if } c \in B - A \\ F_1(c) \cap G_1(c) & \text{if } c \in A \cap B \end{cases}$$

Let $p, q \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$

(i) If $c \in A - B$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{H_1(c)}(p\alpha q) &= \delta_{F_1(c)}(l\alpha m) \\ &\leq \min\{\delta_{F_1(c)}(l), \delta_{F_1(c)}(m)\} \\ &= \min\{\delta_{H_1(c)}(l), \delta_{H_1(c)}(m)\} \end{aligned}$$

(ii) $c \in B - A$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{H_1(c)}(l\alpha m) &= \delta_{G_1(c)}(p\alpha q) \\ &\leq \min\{\delta_{G_1(c)}(p), \delta_{G_1(c)}(q)\} \\ &= \min\{\delta_{H_1(c)}(p), \delta_{H_1(c)}(q)\} \end{aligned}$$

(iii) If $c \in A \cap B$ then $H_1(c) = \max\{F_1(c), G_1(c)\} = \{F_1(c) \cap G_1(c)\}$.

Now using seen that $H_1(c)(l\alpha m) \leq \min\{H_1(c)(l), H_1(c)(m)\}$ for all $l, m \in S$, $\alpha \in \Gamma$ and $c \in C$

$$\delta_{H_1(c)}(l\alpha m) \leq \min\{\delta_{H_1(c)}(l), \delta_{H_1(c)}(m)\}.$$

Hence $(F_1, A) \cap_{\epsilon} (G_1, B)$ is AFS Γ – ideal over S

Theorem 3.18. Let (F_1, A) and (G_1, B) be two AFS Γ – ideal of S, then $(F_1, A) \cap_{\epsilon} (G_1, B)$ and $(F_1, A) \cup_{\epsilon} (G_1, B)$ is AFS Γ – bi-ideal of S.

Proof. The proof is straightforward.

4. Anti fuzzy soft gamma regular semigroups.

In this section S denotes the soft Γ – regular semigroup.

Definition 4.1. A soft Γ – semigroup (F_1, A) over a semigroup S is called a soft Γ – regular semigroup if for each $\alpha, \beta \in A$, $F_1(\alpha, \beta)$ is regular.

Example 4.2. $S = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\}$ and $\Gamma = \{\alpha, \beta\}$ where α, β is defined on S with the following Cayley table:

α	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4
a_1	a_1	a_1	a_1	a_1
a_2	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4
a_3	a_1	a_3	a_3	a_3
a_4	a_1	a_3	a_3	a_3

β	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4
a_1	a_1	a_1	a_1	a_1
a_2	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4
a_3	a_1	a_3	a_3	a_3
a_4	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4

Table-2

Consider $E = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\}$ and $F(a_1) = \{a_1, a_3\}$, $F(a_2) = \{a_2, a_3\}$, $F(a_3) = \{a_1, a_2, a_3\}$, $F(a_4) = \{a_2, a_3, a_4\}$. Hence (F, S) is soft Γ – regular semigroup.

Theorem 4.3. Let (F_1, A) and (G_1, B) be two AFS sets of soft Γ – regular semigroup S and A_1 and A_2 are two non-empty subsets of S .

- (i) $\chi_{A_1}^c \tilde{\cap} \chi_{A_2}^c = \chi_{A_1 \cap A_2}^c$
- (ii) $\chi_{A_1}^c \tilde{\circ} \chi_{A_2}^c = \chi_{A_1 \Gamma A_2}^c$

Proof. Let $p \in A_1 \cap A_2$, then $p \in A_1$ and $p \in A_2$. we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\chi_{A_1}^c \tilde{\cap} \chi_{A_2}^c)(p) &= \max\{\chi_{A_1}^c(p), \chi_{A_2}^c(p)\} \\ &= \max\{0, 0\} \\ &= 0 \\ &= \chi_{A_1 \cap A_2}^c(p) \end{aligned}$$

Suppose $p \notin A_1 \cap A_2$, then $p \notin A_1$ and $p \notin A_2$

$$\begin{aligned} (\chi_{A_1}^c \tilde{\cap} \chi_{A_2}^c)(p) &= \max\{\chi_{A_1}^c(p), \chi_{A_2}^c(p)\} \\ &= \max\{1, 1\} \\ &= 1 \\ &= \chi_{A_1 \cap A_2}^c(p) \end{aligned}$$

(ii) Let $p \in S$, suppose $p \in A_1 \Gamma A_2$, then there exists $a_1 \in A_1$, $\gamma \in \Gamma$ and $a_2 \in A_2$, such that $p = a_1 \gamma a_2$

$$\begin{aligned} (\chi_{A_1}^c \tilde{\circ} \chi_{A_2}^c)(p) &= \inf_{p=c\gamma d} \max\{\chi_{A_1}^c(c) \tilde{\circ} \chi_{A_2}^c(d)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\chi_{A_1}^c(p) \chi_{A_2}^c(p)\} \\ &= \max\{0, 0\} \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Since $1 \geq (\chi_{A_1}^c \tilde{\circ} \chi_{A_2}^c)(p) \geq 0$, hence $\chi_{A_1}^c \tilde{\circ} \chi_{A_2}^c(p) = 0 = \chi_{A_1 \Gamma A_2}^c$

Suppose $p \notin A_1 \Gamma A_2$, then $p \notin a_1 \gamma a_2, a_1 \in A_1, \gamma \in \Gamma$ and $a_2 \in A_2$.

$$\begin{aligned} (\chi_{A_1}^c \overset{\sim}{\circ} \chi_{A_2}^c)(p) &= \max\{\chi_{A_1}^c(p), \chi_{A_2}^c(p)\} \\ &= \max\{1, 1\} \\ &= 1 \\ &= \chi_{A_1 \Gamma A_2}^c(p) \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\chi_{A_1}^c \overset{\sim}{\circ} \chi_{A_2}^c = \chi_{A_1 \Gamma A_2}^c$

The following theorem relation between soft Γ – semigroup and AFS Γ – semigroups.

Theorem 4.4. Let (F_1, A) be a non-empty soft subset of S, (F_1, A) be a soft Γ – subsemigroup of S if and only if $\chi_{F_1(e)}^c$ is AFS Γ – subsemigroup of S.

Proof. Let (F_1, A) be a soft Γ – semigroup of S

$$\chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(e) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } a \in F_1(e) \\ 1 & \text{if } a \notin F_1(e) \end{cases}$$

Let $a, b \in S, \gamma \in \Gamma$ $\chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(a\gamma b) \geq \max\{\chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(a), \chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(b)\}$

then $\chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(a) = 0, \chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(b) = 0$, and $\chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(a\gamma b) = 1$, this implies that $a, b \in F_1(e)$ since

$F_1(e)$ is a Γ – subsemigroup of S, $a\gamma b \in F_1(e)$ and hence $\chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(a\gamma b) = 0$ which is a contradiction.

Thus $\chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(a\gamma b) \geq \max\{\chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(a), \chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(b)\}$ for all $a, b \in F_1(e)$ and $e \in A$.

Conversely assume that $\chi_{F_1(e)}^c$ is AFS Γ – subsemigroup of S. Let $a, b \in F_1(e)$ then $\chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(a) = 0$ and

$\chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(b) = 0, \chi_{F_1(e)}^c$ AFS Γ – subsemigroup.

Now $\max\{\chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(a), \chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(b)\} = 0 \geq \chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(a\gamma b)$ this implies that $\chi_{F_1(e)}^c \lambda(a\gamma b) = 0$ and

hence $a, b \in F_1(e)$ for all $e \in A$. Therefore (F_1, A) is a soft Γ – subsemigroup of S

Theorem 4.5. Let (F_1, A) be a soft Γ – ideal of S if and only if $\chi_{F_1A}^c$ (characteristic function) is AFS Γ – ideal of soft Γ – regular semigroup S.

Theorem 4.6. Let (F_1, B) be a soft Γ – bi-ideal of S if and only if $\chi_{F_1B}^c$ (characteristic function) is AFS Γ – bi-ideal of soft Γ – regular semigroup S.

Theorem 4.7. The following conditions are equivalent

- (i) Every soft Γ -bi-ideal is a soft Γ -ideal of S.
- (ii) Every AFS Γ -bi-ideal of S is a AFS Γ -ideal of S.

Proof. Assume that condition (i) holds, let $\delta_{F_1(e)}$ be any AFS Γ -ideal of S. Let $\delta_{F_1(e)}$ be any AFS Γ -bi-ideal of S, and $p, q \in S$, since the set $(F_1, A) \overset{\sim}{\circ} (S, E) \overset{\sim}{\circ} (F_1, A)$ is a soft Γ -bi-ideal of S, by the assumption is soft Γ -right ideal of S, since S is a soft Γ -regular, we have

$p\Gamma q \in (p\alpha F_1(\alpha, \beta)\beta p)\Gamma q \subseteq p\alpha F_1(\alpha, \beta)\beta p$, there exists $x \in S$ such that $p\Gamma q = p\alpha x\beta p$, since $\delta_{F_1(e)}$ is AFS Γ -bi-ideal of S, for all $e \in A$

Consider

$$\begin{aligned}\delta_{F_1(e)}(p\Gamma q) &= \delta_{F_1(e)}(p\alpha\beta p) \\ &\leq \max\{\delta_{F_1(e)}(p), \delta_{F_1(e)}(p)\} \\ &= \delta_{F_1(e)}(p)\end{aligned}$$

Hence $\delta_{F_1(e)}$ is AFS Γ -right ideal of S. Similarly $\delta_{F_1(e)}$ is AFS Γ -left ideal of S. Therefore $\delta_{F_1(e)}$ is AFS Γ -ideal of S.

Conversely assume that AFS Γ -bi-ideal of S holds. Let (F_1, B) be soft Γ -ideal of S by theorem (4.6) the characteristic function $\chi_{F_1B}^c$ is a AFS Γ -bi-ideal of S. Hence by assumption $\chi_{F_1A}^c$ is AFS Γ -ideal of S, thus by theorem (4.5) $\chi_{F_1A}^c$ is soft Γ -ideal of S.

Hence (ii) $\Rightarrow$ (i)

The following examples shows that AFS Γ -ideal and AFS Γ -bi-ideal of S.

Examples 4.8. Let $S = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\}$ and $\Gamma = \{\alpha, \beta\}$ then S is a Γ -semigroup under the operation defined as in the table.1.

Let $E = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4\}$, $A = \{v_1, v_3\}$ then (F_1, A) is AFS set defined as,

$$\delta_{F_1(v_1)} = \{(a_1, 0.1), (a_2, 0.9), (a_3, 0.3), (a_4, 0.5)\}$$

$$\delta_{F_1(v_3)} = \{(a_1, 0.2), (a_2, 1), (a_3, 0.5), (a_4, 0.7)\}$$

Hence (F_1, A) is AFS Γ -bi-ideal and AFS Γ -ideal over S.

Theorem 4.9. In a soft Γ -regular semigroup S, every AFS Γ -two sided ideal is idempotent.

Proof. Let (F_1, A) be AFS Γ -two sided ideal of S, then by theorem (3.8) $(F_1, A) \approx (F_1, A) \supseteq (F_1, A)$. Since S is soft Γ -regular, $p \in S$, there exists $x \in S$, such that $p = p\alpha\beta p$ for all $e \in A$ we have

$$\begin{aligned}(F_1(e) \approx F_1(e))(p) &= \inf_{p=p\alpha\beta p} \max\{F_1(e)(p\alpha), F_1(e)(p)\} \\ &\leq \max\{F_1(e)(p\alpha), F_1(e)(p)\} \\ &\leq \max\{F_1(e)(p), F_1(e)(p)\} \\ &= F_1(e)(p)\end{aligned}$$

Therefore $(F_1, A) \approx (F_1, A) \subseteq (F_1, A)$.

Hence $(F_1, A) \approx (F_1, A) = (F_1, A)$.

Theorem 4.10. In a soft Γ -regular semigroup S, every AFS Γ -interior ideal is idempotent.

Proof. Let (F_1, A) be AFS Γ -interior ideal of S, then by theorem (3.10)

$(F_1, A) \approx (F_1, A) \supseteq (F_1, A)$. Since S is soft Γ -regular, $p \in S$, there exists $x \in S$, such that

$p = p\alpha\beta p$ for all $e \in A$

we have $p = p\alpha\beta p = p\alpha\beta p\alpha\beta p = ((p\alpha)\beta p\alpha)\beta p$ for all $e \in A$.

$$\begin{aligned}(F_1(e) \approx F_1(e))(p) &= \inf_{p=((p\alpha)\beta p\alpha)\beta p} \max\{F_1(e)((p\alpha)\beta p\alpha), F_1(e)(p)\} \\ &\leq \max\{F_1(e)((p\alpha)\beta p\alpha), F_1(e)(p)\} \\ &\leq \max\{F_1(e)(p), F_1(e)(p)\} \\ &= F_1(e)(p)\end{aligned}$$

Therefore $(F_1, A) \approx (F_1, A) \subseteq (F_1, A)$. Hence $(F_1, A) \approx (F_1, A) = (F_1, A)$.

Theorem 4.11. Every AFS Γ -interior ideal is AFS Γ -ideal over soft Γ -regular semigroup S.

Proof. Let $\delta_{F_1(e)}$ be a soft Γ -ideal of S for all $e \in A$.

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{F_1(e)}(p\alpha q\beta r) &\leq \delta_{F_1(e)}(q\beta r) \text{ since } \delta_{F_1(e)} \text{ is a } \Gamma\text{-left ideal of } S \\ &\leq \delta_{F_1(e)}(q) \text{ since } \delta_{F_1(e)} \text{ is a } \Gamma\text{-right ideal of } S \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\delta_{F_1(e)}(p\alpha q\beta r) \leq \delta_{F_1(e)}(q)$ for all $p, q, r \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Conversely assume that $\delta_{F_1(e)}$ is AFS Γ -interior ideal of S . Let $p, q \in S$ since S is a soft Γ -regular semigroups, there exists $x, y \in S$ such that $p = p\alpha x\beta p$ and $q = q\alpha y\beta q$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Thus we have

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{F_1(e)}(p\Gamma q) &\leq \delta_{F_1(e)}((p\alpha x\beta p)\Gamma q) \\ &= \delta_{F_1(e)}((p\alpha x)\beta p\Gamma q) \\ &\leq \delta_{F_1(e)}(p) \\ \delta_{F_1(e)}(p\Gamma q) &\leq \delta_{F_1(e)}((p\Gamma)q\alpha y\beta q) \\ \text{And} \quad &= \delta_{F_1(e)}((p\Gamma q\alpha)y\beta q) \\ &\leq \delta_{F_1(e)}(q) \end{aligned}$$

Hence proved.

Examples 4.12. Let $S = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\}$ and $\Gamma = \{\alpha, \beta\}$ then S is a Γ -semigroup under the operation defined as in the table.1.

Let $E = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4\}$, $A = \{u_1, u_3\}$ then (F_1, A) is AFS set defined as,

$$\delta_{F_1(u_1)} = \{(a_1, 0.2), (a_2, 0.9), (a_3, 0.5), (a_4, 0.9)\}$$

$$\delta_{F_1(u_3)} = \{(a_1, 0.4), (a_2, 0.8), (a_3, 0.6), (a_4, 0.8)\}$$

Hence (F_1, A) is AFS Γ -interior ideal and Γ -ideal over S .

Theorem.4.13. Let S be a AFS Γ -semigroup. If S is regular then $(F_1, A) = (F_1, A) \circ (S, E) \circ (F_1, A)$.

Proof. Since S is soft Γ -regular, $p \in S$ there exists $x \in S$ such that $p = p\alpha x\beta p$ for all $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma, e \in A$.

Consider

$$\begin{aligned} (F_1(e) \circ S(e) \circ F_1(e))(p) &= \inf_{x=y\Gamma z} \max\{(F_1(e) \circ S(e))(y), F_1(e)(z)\} \\ &\leq \max\{(F_1(e) \circ S(e))(p\alpha x), F_1(e)(p)\} \\ &= \max\left\{ \inf_{p\alpha x=a\Gamma b} \max\{F_1(e)(a) \circ S(e)(b)\}, F_1(e)(p) \right\} \\ &\leq \max\{\max\{F_1(e)(p) \circ S(e)(x)\}, F_1(e)(p)\} \\ &= \max\{\max\{F_1(e)(p) \circ 0\}, F_1(e)(p)\} \\ &= \max\{F_1(e)(p), F_1(e)(p)\} \\ &= F_1(e)(p) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $(F_1, A) \approx (S, E) \approx (F_1, A) \subseteq (F_1, A)$ and by theorem (3.11).

Hence $(F_1, A) \approx (S, E) \approx (F_1, A) = (F_1, A)$.

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References:

1. M. I. Ali, F. Feng, X. Y. Liu and M. Shabir, On some new operations in soft set theory, *Comput. Math. Appl.* 57 1547-1553, (2009).
2. V. Chinnadurai and K. Arulmozhi, Interval valued fuzzy soft semigroups, *Annamalai University science journal* 50 35-44 (2016).
3. Chinram and Jirojkul, on bi-Gamma ideals in Gamma semigroups, *songklanakaran sci .technol journal.* 29, 231-234(2007).
4. P. Dheena and S. Coumaressane, Characterization of regular Gamma semigroups through fuzzy ideals, *Iranian journal of fuzzy systems.* 4(2), 57-68 (2007).
5. P. K. Maji, R. Biswas and R. Roy, Soft set theory, *Comput. Math. Appl.* 45, 555-562 (2003).
6. D. Molodtsov, Soft set theory first results, *Comput. Math. Appl.* 37 19-31(1999).
7. Muhammad Ifran Ali, Muhammad Shabir and K.P. Shum, on soft ideals over semigroups, *Southeast Asian Bulletin of Mathematics.* 34, 595-610 (2010).
8. Muhammad Gulistan, Muhammad Aslam, Saleem Abdullah, Generalized anti fuzzy interior ideals in LA- semigroups, *Applied Mathematics and information science letters an international journal.* 2(3), 1-6 (2014).
9. T. Nagaish, Anti fuzzy bi- Gamma ideals in Gamma semigroups, *International Journal of Algebra* 5 (28), 1387-1394 (2011).
10. Samit kumar majumder, A study of Gamma semigroups in terms of anti fuzzy ideals, *Mathematica Aeterna.* 1 (8)}, 529-536 (2011).
11. S. K Sardar, S. K Majumder and Pavel pal, Characterization of Gamma semigroups in terms of anti fuzzy ideals, *Annals of fuzzy mathematics.* 5(3), 463-473 (2013).
12. M. K. Sen and N. K Saha, On Gamma semigroup, I, *Bull. Calcutta Math. Soc.* 78, 180-186 (1986).
13. M. Shabir and Y.Nawaz, Semigroups characterized by the properties of anti fuzzy ideals, *J. Adv. Res. Pure Math.* 1 (3), 42-59 (2009).
14. Sujit kumar Sardar, On Fuzzy Ideals in Gamma Semigroups, *International Journal of Algebra.* 3 (16), 775 -784 (2009).
15. Thawat changphas and Boonyen thongkam, on soft Gamma semigroups, *Annals of fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics,* 4(2), 217-223 (2012).
16. L. A Zadeh, Fuzzy sets *Inform and control.* 8, 338-353 (1965).